

Acetoacetic Ester Condensation. Preparation of Ethyl 1-Phthalimido-Acetoacetate and 1,3-Diphthalimidoacetoacetate

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Acetoacetic ester condensation of phthalimidoacetic ester in benzene medium in the presence of sodium ethoxide as condensing agent yielded (I) Ethyl 1,3-phthalimidoacetoacetate in 45% yield. Condensation of equimolecular mixture of phthalimidoacetic ester and ethyl acetate under similar conditions gave (IV) Ethyl 1-phthalimidoacetoacetate in 60% yield. Both (I) and (IV) react with ferric chloride to produce blue coloured complexes in ethanolic media.

When esters $RCH_2COOC_2H_5$ and $R'CH_2COOC_2H_5$ are allowed to react with each other in the presence of a condensing agent (sodium ethoxide) there exists a possibility of formation of the following four β -keto esters due to simple and cross condensations.

On condensing ethyl phthalimidoacetate with ethyl acetate in presence of sodium ethoxide, a white needle shaped crystalline compound in 60% yield is obtained, which upon recrystallisation from ethanol melts at 110.5° and therefore, it can not be (II). (I) was prepared by acetoacetic ester condensation of ethyl phthalimidoacetate in the presence of sodium ethoxide, m.p. 192° . The structure of this compound has been confirmed from analytical data.

Therefore, the compound obtained can be either (III) or (IV) which are isomeric in nature and on ketonic hydrolysis, yield the same amino acetone. But (III) in dilute ethanolic solution gives a light red colour with $FeCl_3$ (*loc. cit.*), which on standing gradually changes

1. S. Gabriel and J. Colman *Ber*, 1909, **42**, 1244;

J. K. Mehrotra and S. D. Verma, *This journal*, 1961, **38**, 785

to deep red coloration. The compound obtained above, on the other hand, gives a blue coloration with FeCl_3 . The mixed m.p. of the prepared compound and the authentic compound of (III) was found to be depressed to 90° . These data indicate that the compound obtained is (IV).

Further confirmation of the structures of the compounds (I), (III) and (IV) has been realised through a comparative study of infra-red spectra of these compounds. All these compounds give the usual peaks of phenyl nucleus ($1600, 1464 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and also give peaks of ketonic group (1715 cm^{-1}). The compounds (I) and (IV) give sharp peaks of enolic form of β -keto esters (1645 cm^{-1}). (III) does not give this peak but instead of a little shoulder and a sharp peak of normal ester (1740 cm^{-1}), indicating its non-enolic character which is supported by the gradual deepening of red colour with FeCl_3 in ethanol. The use of (I), (III) and (IV) as potential ligands for metal ions in solution is under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Ethyl 1-phthalimidoacetoacetate: A mixture of phthalimidoacetic ester (23.3 g., 0.1 mole) and pure ethyl acetate (8.8 g., 0.1 mole) was taken in a 500 ml. round bottom flask containing 200 ml. of dry benzene and fitted with a condenser and a CaCl_2 guard tube. 20 ml. of dry ethanol was added through the condenser. Dry pieces of sodium (4.6 g., 0.2 mole) were dropped through the condenser and the mixture warmed gently on a water bath till whole of the sodium has dissolved. The mixture was then refluxed gently for 4 hrs. when a brown viscous mass was obtained. The reaction mixture was cooled and a mixture of 40 ml. acetic acid and 40 ml. water was added to the contents of the flask with brisk shaking. This was warmed on a water bath with occasional shaking till all the brown product had completely decomposed. After cooling, the aqueous layer was separated from the organic layer and from the latter the solvent was removed by distillation under diminished pressure. The residual product was dissolved in hot ethanol and filtered while hot. The filtrate gave needle shaped crystals which upon recrystallisation from ethanol melted at 110.5° , yield 60% (Found: C, 61.51; H, 4.51; N, 5.47; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ requires C, 61.1; H, 4.73; N, 5.09%). The compound is soluble in hot ethanol, glacial acetic acid, benzene and ether. An ethanolic solution gave a blue colour with aqueous FeCl_3 .

The pyrazolone of this compound on recrystallisation from ethanol was obtained as light yellow crystals, m.p. 192° . (Found: C, 67.39; H, 4.26; N, 13.44; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires C, 67.71; H, 4.08; N, 13.17%).

Amino Acetone: Ethyl 1-phthalimidoacetoacetate (27.5 g.) was heated with 30% HCl (200 ml) for 3 hrs. when all the ester had dissolved. The resulting mixture was cooled in ice, when most of the phthalic acid separated. This was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated on a water bath and again chilled in ice. The precipitated phthalic acid was again filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. Extremely hygroscopic hydrochloride of amino acetone thus obtained was dissolved in a small amount of ethanol and precipitated with dry ether, m.p. 75° . (H_2PtCl_6 ; m.p. 189°).

* All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

Ethyl 1-3-diphthalimidoacetoacetate : Phthalimidoacetic ester (11.7 g.) was dissolved in 50 ml of dry benzene by slight warming. 5 ml of dry ethanol was added followed by addition of dry pieces of sodium (1.3 g.). The mixture was gently refluxed (2 hrs.). The slightly viscous brownish mass was decomposed by warming with dilute acetic acid (10 ml. acetic acid and 20 ml. H₂O). The whole was cooled and filtered at the pump. The crystalline product was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 192°; yield 45% (Found : C, 62.67; H, 3.51; N, 6.74. C₂₂H₁₆O₇N₂ requires C, 62.86; H, 3.81; N, 6.67%). The organic layer of the filtrate gave a further quantity of the crude condensed product. This compound is soluble in hot ethanol, glacial acetic acid and an ethanolic solution gave a blue colour with aqueous FeCl₃.

The authors express their deep gratitude to Dr. Arun K. Dey, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, for his interest in the work.

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Received February 1, 1969.